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TOWARD ON-BOARD DETECTION OF ANOMALOUS EVENTS FROM OPS-SAT TELEMETRY USING DEEP LEARNING

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INTRODUCTION

Detecting anomalies from the satellite telemetry is critical for its safe operation. There are three main types of anomalies that should be considered for complex missions: point, collective and contextual. For point anomalies, telemetry values fall outside the nominal range. The collective anomalies refer to the sequences of consecutive telemetry values that are anomalous, whereas in contextual anomalies, single values are anomalous within their local neighborhood. Since there are different types of unexpected events, designing detection systems requires extensive expert knowledge to define nominal ranges of specific telemetry channels and this is often hand-crafted for a specific mission, hence not necessarily generalizable to future spacecraft. To automate the process of anomaly detection from telemetry data, several research venues have been explored. The out-of-limit detection engines can easily spot point anomalies, and various expert systems have been proposed to cover other events. Although there are machine learning algorithms for detecting anomalies from telemetry data, they are commonly heavily parameterized, and incorrect hyperparameters can deteriorate their performance. Recurrent neural networks (RNNs) are particularly suitable for forward prediction based on time series input. An RNN based on Long Short-Term Memory modules is applicable here, as it incorporates temporal learning to elaborate the predicted signal, to confront it with the actual telemetry. The difference between those two can be interpreted as the error between the prediction and the actual signal, and we can use this to detect anomalous events. Such on-board anomaly detection can not only allow us to implement effective Fault Detection, Isolation and Recovery (FDIR) systems, but also reduce the amount of telemetry data that would have to be sent back to Earth for further analysis (it can be interpreted as a smart compression).

Although many approaches to autonomous on-board anomaly detection have already been proposed, most of them have so far only been tested on non-satellite or simulated data [1-3]. The classic approach to telemetry anomalies detection, currently used in real operations of in-orbit spacecraft, is based on manual identification and handling of anomalies. The European Space Agency (ESA) operations team utilizes Anomaly Report Tracking System (ARTS) – a tool that allows operators to mark and track anomalies in the satellites' telemetry data via standard format reports [4]. To identify the possible causes and other effects of the anomalies, another system was developed: DrMUST. It is responsible for performing pattern matching to find similar anomalous behaviors in the spacecraft history [5]. This kind of correlation

analysis makes it possible to determine the main reason of the event and the possibility for the anomaly to happen in the future. However, manual tracking and analysis of the anomalies in the classic approach have many drawbacks. Standard out-of-limit checks are not sufficient to detect less obvious anomalies, and pure human’s work in identification require the team to always have mission experts on board, as abnormal behavior identification requires proficiency in the topic. With the increase in the number of satellites in constellations, the rise in the amount of data generated by spacecraft, and the growing complexity of missions, new solutions are essential to enable rapid response to all events on-board.

Automating the detection of telemetry anomalies brings real benefits to satellite mission operations. As the space market grew, satellites started to generate immensely big amounts of data every day (often in form of multivariate time-series telemetry data). For growing numerous spacecraft missions, it takes a lot of time and effort to download all the data and analyze it manually on the ground. Furthermore, the bandwidth of the radio link is limited, and so is the number of available ground stations. Therefore, automating the process will be inevitable, especially in terms of satellite constellations that continuously generate a lot of data, and long-distance deep space or planets’ exploration missions. The further the satellite or spacecraft is located, the longer it takes to communicate with it for operators on Earth. Without autonomous telemetry anomaly detection, there will be a high risk that the occurring anomaly will have negative consequences on the mission or may result in its premature failure – even before the information about the event will reach operators. Mars or asteroid spacecraft must therefore be able to automatically detect, diagnose, and react to time-critical anomalies and failures [6]. Deep space missions are also more vulnerable to all faults connected to radiation and hostile environmental conditions. Combined with the distance from the operator and the increased fault reaction time (up to several dozen minutes), all solutions accelerating the response to anomaly can save the mission in the event of a failure. Importantly, autonomous anomaly detection can recognize not only the abnormal events themselves but also pre-anomaly events that can precede the actual anomaly [7] and therefore, save the mission before the final fault happens.

In this paper, we discuss our end-to-end pipeline for anomaly detection from the OPS-SAT telemetry using machine learning approaches. Our experiments show how real data can be used to validate the models, as minimizing the number of false alarms plays a pivotal role in practice, because such false alarms would have to be resolved by the FDIR system to avoid any inappropriate action based on wrongly detected anomalies. We will present an array of quantifiable metrics that can be exploited to rigorously verify the models, e.g., before and after compiling them to the target hardware – the algorithms can be verified using a standard workstation, and then they are deployed to the OPS-SAT development kit. It enables us to analyze their capabilities before up-linking the models to the in-orbit satellite, to unchain their abilities in the wild. We will discuss the challenges that are concerned with the characteristics and quality of the real-world telemetry data, together with the importance of performing simulation experiments that offer us the possibility of generating anomalous events with well-known characteristics.

DETECTING ANOMALIES IN OPS-SAT TELEMETRY DATA

The data used for this study was provided by the ESA OPS-SAT team. Additionally, we gathered the list of the most important/interesting telemetry channels that should be analyzed first, among hundreds of other ones. Specifically, we exploited the signals from the magnetometer and the PD values. For the magnetometer signals, they came from the profile called “06_iADCS_cADCS_magnetometer” which is built of the following parameters: I_B_FB_MM_0 (CADC0872), I_B_FB_MM_1 (CADC0873), I_B_FB_MM_2 (CADC0874). For the PD values, the profile called “04_PDangles” was exploited, and the parameters included: I_PD1_THETA (CADC0884), I_PD2_THETA (CADC0886), I_PD3_THETA (CADC0888), I_PD4_THETA (CADC0890), I_PD5_THETA (CADC0892), I_PD6_THETA (CADC0894).

The OPS-SAT data retrieved from the ESA MUST directory (<https://opssat1.esoc.esa.int/webclient-must>) was processed using the KP Labs’ tool for telemetry annotation: Anomaly annotator (<https://anomaly-annotator.kplabs.pl/>, see Fig. 2.). As a result, we identified periodic parts of the channels: CADC0872, CADC0873, CADC0874, CADC0884, CADC0888, CADC0892, CADC0894, and they were split into 1106 segments. All those segments were manually investigated and labeled as anomalous or nominal (see examples in Fig. 3), and later split into the training (829 samples) and validation set (277 segments; see Table 1). The independent test set was developed using the non-periodic parts of those telemetry channels, and it is utilized to investigate the generalization capabilities of the anomaly detectors.

Table 1: The number of anomalous and nominal samples in the training, validation and test sets.

Subset	#Samples	#Anomalous	#Nominal
Training set	829	303	526
Validation set	277	115	162
Test set	341	293	48

Several studies suggested the application of ensemble machine learning models for classifying signals based on the extracted features [8,9] – here, we follow this research pathway and exploit random forests for this task of binary classification (the signal is classified as either nominal or anomalous). We extract an array of features capturing, among others, unwanted peaks in the telemetry signals, their missing parts, or a high level of noise. Additionally, such feature extractors should be robust against different lengths of the signal.

Overall, we exploit the following features, and extract them for each segment:

- **duration** – in seconds,
- **len** – number of data points in a segment,
- **mean** – mean value of the segment values,

Fig. 1. Preview of the example telemetry channels in ESA MUST.

Fig. 2. Data labeling process in the KP Labs’ Anomaly annotator – the data is split into segments and potential anomalies are labeled in red, non-anomalous segments are in green and violet (alternating).

- **var** – variance of the segment values,
- **std** – standard deviation of the segment values,
- **n_peaks** – number of peaks of at least 10% prominence of the segment,
- **smooth10_n_peaks** – number of peaks of at least 10% prominence of the smoothed segment (with the step value of 10),
- **smooth20_n_peaks** – number of peaks of at least 10% prominence of the smoothed segment (step of 20),
- **diff_peaks** – number of peaks of at least 10% prominence of the first derivative of the segment,
- **diff2_peaks** – number of peaks of at least 10% prominence of the second derivative of the segment,
- **diff_var** – variance of the first derivative of the segment values,
- **diff2_var** – variance of the second derivative of the segment values,
- **gaps_squared** – a sum of the squared of the gaps between the data points,

- *len_weighted* – length of the segment corrected using the sampling of the segment,
- *var_div_duration* – variance of the segment values divided by the segment’s duration,
- *var_div_len* – variance of the segment values divided by the length of the segment.

Fig. 3. Randomly selected examples of the nominal telemetry channels from the training set.

EXPERIMENTS

In this study, we are aimed to build a classifier for detecting anomalous parts of the telemetry channels based on the extracted features. To verify the correlation across such manually-crafted features, we extracted the Pearson’s and Spearman’s correlation coefficients (Fig. 4) which indicate that there are strongly correlated features capturing similar signal characteristics. It indicates that performing additional feature selection which commonly follows the feature extraction step in the processing pipeline could help improve the interpretability of the models, as they would be operating on the most discriminative features only. It, however, requires further investigation to make sure that the reduced feature sets do not negatively impact the classification capabilities of the machine learning detection models.

As a classifier, we utilize the default configuration of the random forest model, with the maximum depth of the model restricted to 5. For the validation set, the model reached the accuracy of 0.953, with the precision and recall of 0.964 and

0.922, respectively – the examples of incorrectly classified segments from the validation set are visualized in Figs. 5-6 (false negatives and false positives, respectively). Here, we can appreciate that the incorrectly classified segments would be challenging to the human operators too, as they manifest only subtle characteristics which may indicate that they are nominal (Fig. 5). On the other hand, the false positives (Fig. 6) include the parts of the signal that could indicate that those are abnormal (see e.g., the peaks in the channels rendered in the top row of Fig. 6). Additionally, the most challenging segments include those that are positioned at the “boundary” of the anomalous and nominal parts of the telemetry channel.

Fig. 4. Correlation across the features quantified as the a) Pearson's and Spearman's coefficients for the training set.

In contrast to the training and validation datasets, which were built using the periodic parts of the investigated telemetry channels, the segments for the test set came from other, non-periodic telemetries. This dataset was prepared to check if the classifier provides a robust ability to process such signals as well. Here, the classifier reached the accuracy of 0.938, with precision and recall of 0.986 and 0.942, respectively. The examples gathered in Fig. 7 indicate that the proposed anomaly detection pipeline can indeed be effectively deployed to such non-periodic signals, and can detect its abnormal parts.

CONCLUSIONS

Detecting anomalies in telemetry data captured on-board satellites is a pivotal step toward maintaining their safe and robust operation, and allows us to respond to failures and hazards faster. In this paper, we tackled this issue, and proposed an end-to-end machine learning algorithm for detecting such abnormal signals. The experimental study, performed over real-life OPS-SAT telemetry data showed that our techniques may be effectively deployed to process difficult signal data which is aperiodic and may be incomplete. To fully unchain the potential of such data-driven models, we are currently working on implementing them on board OPS-SAT – this can be a step toward autonomous FDIR systems and smart compression of satellite telemetry before downlinking it to the ground for any further analysis. Finally, our approach allows for classifying the signals (not for determining the exact moment when an anomalous event started occurring) – we are working on coupling it with an algorithm for precisely determining the start of such anomalies [10].

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Fig. 5. Examples of the incorrectly classified anomalous segments from the validation set (false negatives).

Fig. 6. Examples of the incorrectly classified non-anomalous segments from the validation set (false positives).

Fig. 7. Examples of the correctly classified anomalous segments from the test set.

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